

The quality of the Estonian intervocalic /l/ in three quantity degrees

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Abstract

This paper investigates the effect of the surrounding vowel on the quality and duration of the Estonian intervocalic /l/. Previous studies have shown that quantity affects the quality and duration of consonants in Estonian, but how the different enviroing vowels affect the consonant in interaction with three quantity degrees is mostly unclear. The results revealed that in the context of front vowels /e i/ the consonants F1 was lower and F2 higher as compared to back vowels /a u/. The quality of /l/ was affected by quantity, the gender of the subject and the position of the test word in the utterance. The surrounding vowel affected the duration of /l/ in three quantity degrees. The duration of the intervocalic /l/ was longer in the context of high vowels /i u/. Compared to test words in the utterance-medial position, the duration of /l/ was longer in the utterance-final position. Gender affected the duration of /l/, which was shorter for male subjects. The results suggest that the quality and duration of the intervocalic /l/ is dependent on the quality of the enviroing vowels and thus not fixed.

Introduction

This study investigates the quality and duration of the Estonian intervocalic /l/ in three quantity degrees and in two utterance position. Estonian language is one of the few languages that exhibit ternary consonant and vowel length contrast. It has a length opposition of short (Q1), long (Q2) and overlong (Q3) quantity degree, which occur in the primary stressed syllables of a disyllabic foot.

Quantity can be carried by the stressed vowels, consonants or by a combination of both. In this study the quantity is carried by the intervocalic lateral /l/ on the first and second syllable boundary (Q1 [kala] ‘fish’ sg. nom; [vili] ‘grain’ sg. nom; Q2 [kalla] ‘arum’ sg. nom; [villi] ‘decant’ sg. imp; Q3 [kal:la] ‘pour!’ sg. imp; [vil:li] ‘blister’ sg. gen).

The Estonian quantity is affected by the intrinsic duration of the consonants and vowels (Lippus & Šimko, 2015) and the intrinsic duration of the segment is dependent on the place and manner of articulation (Lehiste, 1970). The higher the place of articulation, the shorter the intrinsic duration. Apical consonants have the shortest intrinsic duration and labial consonants have the longest duration (Eek, 1974; Lehiste, 1970). As the place and manner of articulation affect the duration of the segments, it has been shown in Estonian, that the quality of segments is also affected by the quantity (Eek, 1970; Lippus & Šimko, 2015).

Eek (1970) studied the articulation of intervocalic Estonian /l/ in the context of the vowel /a/, in three quantity degrees using the palatograph and the roentgenograph. The alveolar contact in the Q2 was anterior than the contact in Q3. Posterior alveolar contact in Q3 was accompanied by a wider lateral contact. This articulatory compensation shows that the Q3 is articulated with a higher articulatory strain than Q2. The tongue as a whole is more involved in the process of articulation. The quantity affects the place of articulation and thus the quality of /l/.

In a continuous speech stream segments tend to be coarticulated and this

coarticulation of segments brings about a change in quality. Öhman (1966) studied the formant patterns of /b g d/ in VCV utterances read by Swedish, American and Russian test subjects. The F2 of voiced stops were higher with high vowels and lower with low vowels. He, and other researchers agree, that this due to the partial adjusting that is made when anticipating the next phoneme (Purcell, 1979; Recasens, 1984). Purcell (1979) corroborated Öhmans (1966) findings and added that the vowel adjacent to the consonant has a bigger influence on the formant structure than the vowel following the consonant.

It is known that the segments in the end of the utterance tend to have a longer duration (Berkovits, 1993; Cooper & Danly, 1981; Lehiste, 1970), yet it is unclear how or whether the quality is affected. As previous research on the quality of /l/ is limited to only two vowels /a/ or /i/, the vowels that surround /l/ in this study are the primary vowels /a e i u/ which can occur both in stressed and unstressed syllables. Thus, reasearch questions in this study are:

- 1) Do the surrounding vowels affect the quality of /l/?
- 2) Does the quantity and surrounding vowels affect the duration of /l/?
- 3) Does the position of the test word in the utterance affect the quality and quantity of /l/?

Materials and method

Subjects

12 native Estonians (6 female and 6 male) with the mean age of 25 participated in the experiment. The youngest subject was 19 and the oldest was 55 years old. The subjects did not report any hearing or visual impairments. The subjects spoke Standard Estonian.

Materials

The material consisted of 12 test words (table 1) that were embedded in a four-

word carrier sentences, in which the studied disyllabic test words ((C)VC(C)V) were in the utterance medial and final position. Altogether 288 test words were analyzed (12x24). The data for this study can be found at <https://datadoi.ut.ee/handle/33/67>.

Table 1: Test words in three quantity degrees, which were used in the experiment. * denotes a proper name

Vowel	Q1	Q2	Q3
/a/	kala	kalla	kalla
/e/	Hele*	Elle*	lelle
/i/	vili	villi	villi
/u/	tulu	mullu	hullu

Method

The data were recorded in 2014 in a soundproof recording booth with a DPA-4088-F34 microphone and processed through a Sound Devices USB-Pre soundcard. The subjects were asked to read the test words appearing in a random order on a computer screen using the Speechrecorder (Draxler & Klaus Jänsch, 2014) software.

Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2014) was used to manually annotate the onsets and offsets of vowels and consonants, the quantity and the position of the word in the utterance. Praat script was used to extract the duration of the segments and the F1 and F2 values with a 10% step from the whole duration of the segment. The values from 40-70% were summarized and used for analysis.

A Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) with a Poisson family with a log link was used for the statistical analysis conducted in R (Team, 2013). In the GLMM, the dependent variables were F1, F2 and the duration of /l/. The independent variables were the quantity degrees (Q1, Q2, Q3), vowel (/a e i u/), gender (male (M) and female (F)) and the position of the test word (utterance-medial (UM) and final (UF)). The test subject was used as a random effect. The intercept for the model was the utterance-

final test word in the context of /a/ by female subject in Q1.

Results

Quality of the intervocalic /l/

To give an overview on how the quality of /l/ was affected by the vowels and quantity, figure 1 was plotted.

Figure 1. The quality of /l/ (in Hertz and Bark) in three quantity degrees (Q1 black, Q2 red, Q3 green) surrounded by /a e i u/, articulated by female subjects in utterance-medial position. V1 and /l/ marked with a letter, V2 without.

The general tendencies for males and females were the same, so only the data from female speakers was chosen to be presented here. The quality of /l/ was affected by the vocalic context. F1 of /l/ was lower with high vowels /i u/ and F2 was higher with lower vowels /a e/. Figure 1 also suggests that quantity affects the quality of /l/. To test these assumptions bar plots were plotted (figure 2, 3) and GLMM-s were calculated for F1 and F2 of /l/.

F1 of the intervocalic /l/

Output of GLMM (intercept $\beta=6.37$) for the F1 of /l/, as supported by figure 2, confirmed that quantity affected the quality of /l/. Quantity lowered F1, which was lowest with Q2 ($\beta=-0.07$, $p<0.006$) and lower with Q3 ($\beta=-0.05$, $p<0.04$).

Figure 2. Means of F1 (in Hertz) of /l/ in three quantity degrees (Q1 black, Q2 gray, Q3 light gray) surrounded by /a e i u/, articulated by female and male subjects in utterance-final and medial positions.

Vowel context also affected the F1 of /l/, which was lowest in the context of high vowels /i u/ respectively, as compared to intercept ($\beta=-0.39$, $p<0.001$; $\beta=-0.24$, $p<0.001$). F1 values of /l/ in the context of /e/ were similar to /u/ ($\beta=-0.22$, $p<0.001$)

Male speakers had a lower F1 than female speakers (M $\beta=-0.11$, $p<0.001$) and utterance-medial test words had a higher F1 ($\beta=0.1$, $p<0.001$).

Male speakers had a lower F1 in the interaction between quantity, high vowels /i u/ and gender. This was evident with vowels /i u/ in Q2 ($\beta=0.19$, $p<0.001$, $\beta=0.32$, $p<0.001$), and with /i/ in Q3 ($\beta=0.13$, $p<0.02$).

The position of the test word in the utterance affected the quality of F1. There were significant interactions between quantity, vowels and the position of the test word. In Q2 utterance-medial test word the F1 of /l/ was higher with high vowels /i u/ ($\beta=0.16$, $p<0.005$, $\beta=0.25$, $p<0.001$). In Q3 utterance-medial test word the F1 of /l/ was higher with vowels /e i u/ ($\beta=0.23$, $p<0.001$, $\beta=0.18$, $p<0.001$, $\beta=0.36$, $p<0.001$).

Between males and females, the F1 of the utterance-medial test word of male speakers was significantly lower

only in the context of /u/ in Q2 ($\beta=-0.24$, $p<0.002$) and Q3 ($\beta=-0.33$, $p<0.001$).

F2 of the intervocalic /l/

Output of GLMM (intercept $\beta=7.14$) for the F2 of /l/, which is supported by figure 3, also confirmed that quantity affected F2, which was higher with Q2 ($\beta=0.12$, $p<0.001$) and highest with Q3 ($\beta=0.15$, $p<0.001$).

Figure 3. Means of F1 (in Hertz) of /l/ in three quantity degrees (Q1 black, Q2 gray, Q3 light gray) surrounded by /a e i u/, articulated by female and male subjects in utterance-final and medial positions.

Vowel context affected the F2 of /l/, which was higher with front vowels /e i/ ($\beta=0.36$, $p<0.001$; $\beta=0.5$, $p<0.001$) and lower with back vowel /u/ ($\beta=0.1$, $p<0.001$). Utterance-medial test word was articulated with a higher F2 ($\beta=0.07$, $p<0.001$).

Gender as a main effect did not affect F2 in a significant way, but it did have two, three and four-way significant interactions with quantity, vowels and position of the test word. Compared to female speakers, the F2 values of male subjects were lower in the utterance-medial position in the interaction with vowel and quantity.

Only interactions that were not significant in that four-way interaction GLMM were between high front vowel /i/ and utterance-medial test word ($\beta=-0.02$, $p<0.33$), and also high vowel /i/, utterance-medial test word, Q2 and Q3

interactions ($\beta=0.03$, $p<0.25$; $\beta=-0.03$, $p<0.28$). The interaction between high back vowel /u/ in the utterance-medial position uttered by male speakers in Q2 and Q3 was also not significant ($\beta=0.03$, $p<0.3$; $\beta=-0.09$, $p<0.006$).

Duration of the intervocalic /l/

Output of the GLMM (intercept $\beta=4.1$), which is supported by figure 4, reported that duration of the intervocalic /l/ grew exponentially quantity, being longer with Q2 ($\beta=0.95$, $p<0.001$) and longest with Q3 ($\beta=1.2$, $p<0.001$).

Figure 4. The duration (in milliseconds) of /l/ surrounded by /a e i u/, in three quantity degrees and in utterance-medial and final positions, uttered by male and female subjects.

The duration of /l/ was longer with high vowels /i u/ ($\beta=0.08$, $p<0.05$; $\beta=0.09$, $p<0.04$). Compared to female speakers, the duration /l/ of the male speakers was shorter ($\beta=-0.06$, $p<0.004$). Intervocalic /l/ was shorter in the utterance-medial position ($\beta=0.07$, $p<0.001$).

The duration of /l/ was shorter in the front vowel and quantity interactions. Q2 /l/ in the context of /e/ was shorter compared to Q3 /l/ in the context of /e/ ($\beta=-0.19$, $p<0.001$; Q3:/e/ ($\beta=-0.15$, $p<0.001$). Compared to the intercept, the duration of Q3 /l/ in the context of /i/ was shorter ($\beta=-0.09$, $p<0.03$).

The duration of /l/ was different between males and females only in the vowel /u/ interaction with male speakers where the duration was shorter ($\beta=-0.06$, $p<0.004$). /l/ in the context of vowel /i/ was longer in the utterance medial position ($\beta=0.06$, $p<0.04$).

Discussion

The results of this study are in line with previous studies, which show that the vocalic context influences the quality and quantity of the consonant, but it also gives new insight into the coarticulatory effects of the vowels onto the consonant. Previous studies (Eek, 1970, 1974) in Estonian have been conducted mostly with restricted vocalic context /a/ or as in a more recent study only the contrast between /a/ and /i/ was studied (Lippus & Šimko, 2015). This study analyzed the effects of the four primary vowels /a e i u/ that can occur both in the first and second syllable, which gives a broader overview of the coarticulatory effect.

The results showed that the place of articulation of vowels influence the place of articulation of /l/. In a continuous stream of speech, the articulators do not have the time to fully reach their designated destinations and an economical compromise is made. The higher and more fronted the vowels place of articulation, the higher and more fronted the place of articulation of /l/ was. This allows for a faster transition from a vowel to consonant.

Arvo Eek (1970) observed in his articulatory study that the quantity influences the quality of sonorants. /l/ in Q2 had a smaller lateral distribution on the palate of the mouth than Q3. He also observed that the anterior place of articulation of /l/ was anterior in Q2 than in Q3. This was also evident from the formant patterns of /l/ as quantity affected the quality of /l/ in this study. In Q2, the F1 of /l/ was higher than in Q3, which might be linked to an anterior place of articulation in Q2. With F2 of /l/, the formant

frequencies rose exponentially with quantity in this study.

It is a well-known fact in Estonian that the quantity affects the duration of the consonant on the first and second syllable boundary, but how different vocalic context affects the duration of the /l/ in three quantity degrees has not been systematically studied in Estonian. The results in this study are in line with the theory of intrinsic duration of segments (Lehiste, 1970) which states that the higher and more fronted the vowel is the shorter the duration. This psycho-acoustic effect makes us perceive vowels, which are articulated with a higher articulatory strain, longer. This can be confirmed, as in the context of high vowels /i u/ the duration of /l/ was longer in this study.

The position of the test word in the utterance affected the quality and duration of the test word. Utterance-medial /l/ was articulated with a higher F1 and F2 values and with a shorter duration. The reason for this is that utterance-final test words tend to be lengthened and articulated with a lower articulatory energy.

As females usually have a longer and narrower vocal tract, expectedly, their formant values were higher compared to male subjects. Interestingly, gender affected the duration of /l/, which was shorter for male subjects.

Conclusions

The quality of the intervocalic /l/ was affected by the surrounding vowels. In the context of front vowels /e i/ the consonants F1 were lower and F2 were higher as compared to back vowels /a u/. The quantity affected the quality of /l/. F1 of /l/ was lowest with Q2 and lower with Q3. F2 was higher with higher quantity degree.

The position of the test word affected the quality of F1 and F2 of /l/. As a main effect, the F1 and F2 were higher in the utterance-medial position but varied in the interaction with other factors.

Expectedly, gender affected the F1 and F2 values of /l/, which were lower for male speakers.

The quantity affected the duration of /l/, which grew exponentially with quantity and was longest in Q3. /l/ in the utterance final test word was longer than in median position. /l/ was longer in the context of high vowels /i u/. The duration of /l/ was affected by gender, which was shorter when articulated by male speakers.

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